

Reactions of (*p-m- and -o-*) Trimethylsilyl benzyl Bromides*

K. Dey

Some reactions of (*para-*, *meta-* and *ortho-*) trimethylsilyl benzyl bromides with pyridine have been studied.

The reaction between aforesaid isomeric-organosiliconbenzyl bromides with freshly distilled pyridine in dry benzene gives light brown shining flakes, which are highly soluble in water, but comparatively less soluble in organic solvents. The elemental analyses corresponds to the following formulation for the isolated compounds :

The water solutions of the compounds react with Ag^+ ion to produce AgBr . It seems likely that the isomeric trimethylsilylbenzyl carbonium ion is stabilized by the nucleophilic character of pyridine, thereby producing corresponding pyridinium salts.-

Table 1 records some important infrared spectral bands for [*p*- $\text{Me}_3\text{Si} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{N}^+\text{C}_5\text{H}_5$] Br^- with their probable assignments. Medium intensity bands around $3020\text{--}3030\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be considered as C-H stretching frequency and is comparable with C-H stretch of the pyridine itself¹. In pyridine hydrochloride C-H stretch observed² around 3030 cm^{-1} . The C=C and C=N stretching vibrations along with ring stretch are recorded at 1635 cm^{-1} , 1580 cm^{-1} and 1490 cm^{-1} , which is about $10\text{--}5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ higher than the pyridine itself, but quite similar to that of pyridine hydrochloride¹⁻³. A medium intensity band was observed at 1405 cm^{-1} , which we believe to be due to deformation of C-H of CH_2 adjacent to N^+ . Similar assignments were done by Nakanishi³. Another medium intensity band around 1310 cm^{-1} may be taken as suggestive of the presence of C-N stretching vibration of tertiary aromatic amine. Other peaks recorded in Table 1 are self explanatory.

From the analytical and infrared spectra data of the compounds one would expect that isomeric- trimethylsilylbenzyl pyridinium bromides are formed by the reactions of isomeric trimethylsilylbenzyl bromides with pyridine under the present reaction conditions.

* This work was carried out in the Department of Chemistry, University of Sussex, Brighton, England. Author is grateful to Professor C. Eaborn for laboratory facilities.

1. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared spectra of Complex Molecules", London; Methuen and Co. Ltd., New York, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1960, p. 277.
2. N. B. Colthum, L. J. Daly and S. E. Wiberly, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1964, p. 393.
3. K. Nakanishi, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Practical, Nankodo Company Ltd., Tokyo, 1966, pp. 39, 158 and 160.

TABLE 1

Some important I.R. bands of [p-Me₃SiC₆H₄CH₂N⁺C₅H₅]Br⁻

Bands; Cm ⁻¹	Intensity	Assignments
3020—3030 (Multiplets)	Medium	C-H stretching vibrations.
1635	Medium } Weak } Medium }	C = C and C = N stretching vibrations and ring stretch.
1580		
1490		
1405	Medium	Deformation of C-H of CH ₂ - adjacent to N ⁺
1310	Medium	C-N stretching vibration due to tertiary aromatic amine.
1170	Medium }	C-H in plane deformations due to 1 : 4 disubstitutions.
1105		
810	Medium	2 adjacent-H; C-H out of plane deformations due to 1 : 4 disubstitutions.
690	Strong	5 adjacent-H, wagging due to the presence of pyridine.
1250	very strong	Me ₃ Si : Symmetrical CH ₃ deformation.
845	very strong	Me ₃ Si : Si -CH ₃ stretch.
770	very strong	Me ₃ Si : Si -CH ₃ stretch.

Further work on the reaction of carbon-functional organosilicon and—tin compounds with heterocyclic bases and also further work on the present compounds is in progress and will be communicated in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls using a Perkin Elmer 257 Infrared Grating spectrophotometer.

Solvents used were purified and dried by standard methods before use.

Elemental analyses of the compounds were carried out by the Microanalysts of Sussex University, England.

Preparation of the starting materials: Isomeric tolyltrimethylsilanes and isomeric trimethylsilylbenzyl bromides were prepared by the published methods⁴⁻⁶.

Reaction of p-trimethylsilylbenzyl bromide with pyridine (0.01 molar scale): An equimolar mixture of *p*-trimethylsilylbenzyl bromide and freshly distilled pyridine in dry benzene (~ 7 ml) was heated on water-bath for one hour, which on standing for 8 days yielded (90%)

- H. Frieser, M. V. Eagle and J. Speier, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2821.
- H. A. Clark, A. F. Gordon, C. W. Young and M. J. Hunter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 3798.
- R. G. Severson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 6540.

light brown shining flakes. It was recrystallized from chloroform (m.p. 201–202°). It is highly soluble in water, but comparatively less so in organic solvents. Found : C, 55.46; H, 6.29; N, 4.47%. Calcd. for $(\text{SiC}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{N Br})$: C, 55.89; H, 6.21; N, 4.34%.

Reaction of m-trimethylsilylbenzyl bromide with pyridine (0.01 molar scale) : By an analogous method, *m*-trimethylsilylbenzyl pyridinium bromide, a yellow crystalline solid was isolated in 68% yield. It was recrystallized from chloroform (m.p. 208–211°) and was highly soluble in water. Found : C, 55.58; H, 6.18; N, 4.39%. Calculated for $(\text{SiC}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{N Br})$: C, 55.89; H, 6.21; N, 4.34%.

Reaction of o-trimethylsilylbenzyl bromide with pyridine (0.01 molar scale) : Under the above conditions a yellow solid product was isolated by reacting *o*-trimethylsilylbenzyl bromide and pyridine in 39% yield. It was recrystallized from chloroform (m.p. 188–190°). It is highly soluble in water. Found : C, 55.22; H, 5.99; N, 4.32%. Calculated for $(\text{SiC}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{N Br})$: C, 55.89; H, 6.21; N, 4.34%.

Department of Chemistry,
University of Kalyani,
Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal.

Received April 30, 1970